

Design and Fabrication of Cost-Effective Electro-Magnetic Braking System

Abhishek U ¹, Dev Muneeshwar G ¹, Kushal M S ¹, Anish Krishna R ¹,
Arunkumar H^{*2}

¹.UG Scholars, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University,

^{*2}Assistant Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University.

ABSTRACT

Majority of braking systems work on the principle of dissipation of kinetic energy to heat energy. This method has its own drawbacks and must be replaced with a more reliable braking system that is quick in response, doesn't heat up and is maintenance free. In this project the design of an electro-magnetic braking system and optimization for various operational parameters has been done and the advantage of using the electromagnetic braking system in automobile is studied. These parameters have been previously iterated in cited projects and papers and also in the simulation models and are to be cross-checked with the experimental setup. An Electromagnetic Braking system uses Magnetic force to engage the brake, but the power required for braking is transmitted manually. The wheel is connected to a shaft and the electromagnet braking unit is attached to one side of the wheel. Here the braking unit consists of a hollow circular steel plate and a stator which has 3 spokes made of iron wound with copper wire (or) magnetic wire. Here the round steel plate which is attached to the wheel rotates when wheel rotates with the help of motor. when current is supplied to the stator the spokes get magnetized and creates a magnetic field which tries to attract or oppose the motion of rotating circular plate with the help of magnetic field created. In these brakes there is no contact between the electro-magnetic coils and rotating circular plate (i.e 2mm gap between coil and circular plate) so this is also called as contactless braking system which is a main advantage in using these brakes. In this these brakes can be incorporated in heavy vehicles as an auxiliary brake.

Keywords: Braking System, Magnetic Field, Stator

1. INTRODUCTION

An electromagnetic braking system is a sophisticated technology used in vehicles and machinery to slow down or stop motion by converting kinetic energy into electrical energy through the principles of electromagnetism. This innovative braking mechanism offers several advantages over traditional friction based systems, including enhanced efficiency, precise control, and reduced wear and tear on braking components. The fundamental operation of an electromagnetic braking system involves the interaction between a magnetic field and an electric current, creating resistance that opposes the motion of the object. Typically, these systems consist of a magnetized rotor, a stator with electromagnets, and a control unit. During braking, the electromagnets within the stator are energized by an electric current, generating a magnetic field. As the rotating rotor passes through this magnetic field, it experiences electromagnetic induction, which generates eddy currents within the rotor. These eddy currents create an opposing magnetic field, resulting in a braking force that decelerates the rotor's rotation. The strength of the braking force can be precisely controlled by adjusting the intensity of the electric current supplied to the electromagnets, allowing for smooth and responsive braking performance. Additionally, electromagnetic braking systems offer regenerative braking capabilities, meaning they can convert kinetic energy into electrical energy, which can be stored or reused, thus improving overall energy efficiency.

Electro-mechanical disk brakes operate via electrical actuation, but transmit torque mechanically. When electricity is applied to the coil of an electromagnet, the magnetic flux attracts the armature to the face of the brake. As it does so, it squeezes the inner and outer friction disks together. The hub is normally mounted on the shaft that is rotating. The brake housing is mounted solidly to the machine frame. As the disks are squeezed, torque is transmitted from the hub into the machine frame, stopping and holding the shaft.

Working principle:

Electromagnetic brakes work on the principle of electromagnetic induction. If a metallic disc or a coil is rotating in a uniform magnetic field, it will experience a torque due to induced currents set up in the disc. According to Lenz's law, induced current is in a direction so as to oppose the rotation. Hence a retarding torque is produced. The rotating wheel of a vehicle is connected to a coil placed in a uniform emf is used to charge a battery. Thus, kinetic energy of wheel is stored as chemical energy. The drawback of electromagnetic brake is that induced current or retarding torque is directly proportional to speed of rotation. The speed, therefore, decays exponentially and vehicle will take a long time to stop. Thus, mechanical brakes are used simultaneously.

Fig1: electromagnetic braking system

Fig2: Metal Wheel

METHODOLOGY**Fig3: Methodolgy****2. CALCULATIONS:-**

775 Motor DC 12V-36V
3500-9000 RPM

Shaft dia -5mm
 $r = 5/2 = 2.5\text{mm} = 0.0025\text{m}$
 given torque:-
 $1\text{kg.cm} = 0.0981\text{ Nm}$
 i.e , $2\text{kg.cm} = 0.1962\text{ Nm}$

torque = force * radius

$$\text{force} = \frac{\text{torque}}{\text{radius}}$$

$$= \frac{0.1962}{0.0025} = 78.48\text{N}$$

$$\text{Power} = \frac{\text{torque} * \text{angular speed}}{2 * 3.14}$$

$$\text{Avg. RPM} = \frac{3500 + 9000}{2}$$

$$2 = 6250 \text{ RPM}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Power} = \frac{0.1962 * 2 * 3.14 * 6250 / 60}{2 * 3.14}$$

$$P = \frac{0.1962 * 6250}{60} \text{ W}$$

$$P = \frac{1226.25}{60} \text{ W}$$

$$P = 20.437 \text{ W}$$

Therefore, the power of 775DC motor is approximately 20.437 W

Electromagnet Coil:-

Number of turns in coil-600

Magnetic flux density of Metal wheel:-(B)

$$B = \mu * N$$

$$B = 0.994 * 600$$

$$B = 600 \text{ H/m}$$

(N=number of turns in coil)

(μ =Relative permeability of copper wire)

(H=Henris)

Braking Force:-

$$F = B * A$$

$$F = 600 * \pi * 0.09^2$$

$$F = 15.2681 \text{ N}$$

Velocity:-

$$V = 0.09 * \pi * \frac{\text{RPM}}{60}$$

$$V = 0.09 * \pi * \frac{3500}{60}$$

$$V = 32.98 \text{ m/s}$$

Energy Conversion:-

$$P = F * V$$

$$P = 15.2681 * 32.98$$

$$P = 276.15$$

$$P = 0.276 \text{ W}$$

(Convert mm to m by dividing 1000)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results and discussion of an electromagnetic braking system will focus on the performance, total deformation, equivalent Elastic strain and stress.

Total deformation in an electromagnetic braking system refers to the overall change in shape or distortion experienced by its components during operation. This deformation can occur due to various factors, including mechanical forces, thermal effects, and electromagnetic forces.

The equivalent elastic strain in an electromagnetic braking system refers to the deformation or strain experienced by the system's components due to mechanical loading, thermal effects, or electromagnetic forces, which can be characterized as if the material were purely elastic.

Equivalent stress in an electromagnetic braking system refers to the simplified representation of the complex stress distribution within the system. It's derived from various stress components, such as mechanical, thermal, and electromagnetic forces, and represents the combined effect of these stresses on the material.

The provided analysis outlines an investigation into the electromagnetic braking system, with emphasis on assessing total deformation with the maximum of 4.6168×10^{-12} and minimum of 0, stress with the maximum of 0.0030605 and minimum of 6.0411×10^{-12} , and strain with the maximum of 1.5321×10^{-12} and minimum of 3.1034×10^{-17} . The electromagnet remains fixed while loads are applied at the four corners of the model, simulating real-world conditions. Torque is applied of 0.2N-m to replicate the rotational forces acting on the wheel, treating it as a unified element within the system with the braking force of 78.48N.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The electromagnetic braking system is found to be reliable and efficient compared to other braking systems. In an oil based braking system or an air-conditioning braking system, minor leaks may lead to complete failure of the brakes. Although the electromagnetic braking coil and shooting circuits are connected separately on each wheel, any damaged or failing coil brakes do not fail completely as the remaining three coils work properly. And this program needs very little adjustment. In addition, it is found that electric brakes form approximately 80 percent of the total energy used by the brakes. Electric brakes are used as additional reversal brakes in addition to normal collisions with heavy vehicles. Friction brakes can be used sparingly and therefore do not reach very high temperatures. Brakes will last longer before they need extra care and the potential problem of brake fade can be avoided and thus more economical.

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